

Privacy Preservation in Textual Data: A Systematic Mapping Study on Differential Privacy and Semantic Similarity

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Selection Criteria - Exclusion Criteria(EC) Studies were excluded if they meet any criteria in Table 1.

Table 1. Exclusion Criteria (EC)

EC	Criteria
EC-1	Do not involve textual data (e.g., focus exclusively on image, audio, or structured tabular data).
EC-2	Lack relevance to semantic text similarity , rarity-aware analysis , and/or privacy-preserving techniques in the context of textual data analysis .
EC-3	Are non-peer-reviewed , such as informal blog posts, promotional white papers, or internal reports, unless cited by multiple peer-reviewed sources.
EC-4	Duplicates of previously screened studies.
EC-5	Full text not accessible.